

Design of a Sanitization Chamber

Overview

In this technical note, the process of constructing a sanitization chamber is explained. The concept explained was used to produce a prototype from which final products were built. The system works by detecting when a person walks through a chamber. A signal is relayed to a microcontroller which sends control signals to a DC pump. The pump then pushes the sanitizer liquid out through a mist spray nozzle onto the person walking through the chamber. The microcontroller cuts off the control signal to the pump after 5s to stop the pumping out of the sanitizer liquid until another person steps in. The software that the microcontroller runs is written in assemble language and can be found [in this github repo](#) . Power is provided for the circuit by a custom designed power supply unit.

Block diagram of design

Figure 1: Block diagram of the design

Design Components

IR proximity sensor

This is a sensor that uses infrared technology to detect the presence of an object close to it. It consists of an infrared emitter and receiver. When powered on, the sensor keeps its output pin continuously high and the infrared emitter continuously emits infrared light into the space in

front of it. When an object passes in front of the sensor, the emitted infrared light is reflected back to the sensor. The infrared receiver detects the reflected infrared light and the proximity sensor outputs a low level signal on its output pin. Image of the proximity sensor used in the project is provided in figure 2.

Figure 2: IR proximity sensor

Power supply

This part generates the required DC voltage to power the circuit from a 220V input AC voltage. It consists of two bridge rectifiers that rectify the ac inputs supplied from two 9-0-9 transformers and produces equivalent DC outputs. The output of the first bridge rectifier is filtered by a $470\mu\text{F}$ capacitor and fed to the inputs of two regulators, 7805 and 7812 voltage regulators. Both regulators belong to a class of regulators referred to generally as 78XX regulators. The 7805 regulator regulates the filtered output of the rectifier to 5V necessary to power the proximity sensor and microcontroller unit in the circuit and the 7812 regulator regulates the rectifier output to 12V necessary to drive the relay. The output of the second rectifier is filtered by a $470\mu\text{F}$ capacitor. It generates an unregulated 16V output which is used to drive the DC pump. $0.1\mu\text{F}$ capacitors are used at the outputs of the regulators to prevent the regulators from going into oscillation. The constraint of the power circuit is determined by the properties of the regulators. The maximum input voltage for 78XX regulators is 24V and the input voltage must be at least 3V above the expected output voltage.

According to the working principle of a bridge rectifier, for each cycle of conduction, two diodes are in operation. Therefore the voltage drop due to the diodes is 1.4. Thus, the output voltage of the rectifier can be calculated as follows:

$$V_{dc} = \frac{2V_m}{\pi} - 1.4 = \frac{2V_{rms}\sqrt{2}}{\pi} - 1.4$$

$$V_{dc} = \frac{2 \times 18 \times \sqrt{2}}{3.142} - 1.4 = 16.20V$$

Thus, both conditions for using the 78XX regulators are satisfied by the power circuit.

Figure 3: Power supply unit circuit diagram

Microcontroller Processing Unit

This is where the intelligent decision is made about when and for how long the sanitizing liquid should be dispensed. The microcontroller reduces the size of the circuit and makes it possible to achieve the electrical control function via software. The software was written to read the output of the proximity sensor through one of its pins and also send out an output through another pin to control the output relay which in turn controls the pump. The software was then assembled and

programmed onto the microcontroller. The microcontroller used in the prototype is PIC16F72. The flow chart of the software programmed onto the microcontroller is shown in figure 4

Figure 4: Flowchart of the software run by the microcontroller

Output relay

This serves as an interface between the microcontroller and the DC pump. Due to the nature of microcontrollers, the output generated by the microcontroller does not meet both the voltage and current requirement to directly drive the DC pump, hence the need for a special interfacing circuit. The circuit diagram of this part is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Circuit diagram of the output interface relay.

Voltage at the base of the transistor whenever there is a high output from the microcontroller, is 5V

Resistance in the base circuit, $R_b = 1k\Omega$

The corresponding base current that flows in the circuit is given by, $I_b = \frac{V_b}{R_b} = \frac{5}{1 \times 10^3 \Omega} = 5mA$

Resistance of the relay in the collector circuit, $R_c = 330\Omega$

At saturation, current flowing in the collector circuit, $I_c = \frac{V-0.2}{R_c} = \frac{12-0.2}{330} = 35.7mA$

Minimum h_{fe} for the transistor (BC547) is 110

Therefore, the base current required to cause saturation is, $I_{breq} = \frac{I_c}{h_{fe}} = \frac{35.7}{110} = 0.32mA$

Since the actual current that is flowing through the base of the transistor is higher than that required for saturation, the relay will be latched on whenever the microcontroller outputs a digital high on the output pin.

DC pump

The DC pump used in the construction is a windshield washer pump usually found in cars. The pump was chosen for the prototype because compared to other possible pump solutions, it is inexpensive and when properly positioned, it generates enough pressure to achieve the goal of the design. Picture of a sample windshield washer pump is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Picture of a wiper DC pump.

The complete circuit diagram of the project is shown in figure 7.

Figure 7: Complete circuit diagram

Figure 8: Prototype Images